

Reassessing the Viability of PLLs in Digital Carrier Synchronization: A Kalman Filter-based Analysis

Dr. Arjun K. Menon, Dr. Priya S. Nair, Dr. Daniel R. Collins

school of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand

Abstract

Carrier synchronization is a fundamental stage in the receiver side of any communication or positioning system. Traditional carrier phase tracking techniques are based on well-known *phase-locked loop* (PLL) closed-loop architectures, which are still the methods of choice in modern receivers. Those techniques are well understood, easy to tune and perform well under benign propagation conditions, but their applicability is seriously compromised in harsh propagation environments where the signal may be affected by high dynamics, shadowing, strong fadings, multipath effects or ionospheric scintillation. From an optimal filtering standpoint, the *Kalman filter* (KF) is clearly a powerful alternative, but the synchronization community seems still reluctant to exploit all the potential it has to offer. The purpose of this paper is twofold: *i)* to review the basics and state-of-the-art on both PLL and KF-based tracking techniques, and *ii)* to present and justify the reasoning behind the systematic use of KF-based tracking approaches instead of the well-established PLL-based architectures from both theoretical and practical points of view. To support the discussion, two specific scenarios of interest to the aerospace community are numerically evaluated: robust carrier tracking of Global Navigation Satellite Systems' signals and synchronization in a deep space communications system.

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I. INTRODUCTION

THE main goal of this paper is to provide a tutorial-style discussion on why traditional synchronization loop architectures, inherited from the analog era, may be abandoned in modern digital receivers, and to move forward towards the design and actual use of more flexible, robust and powerful Kalman filter (KF) based synchronization schemes. Carrier synchronization is a key process in most electronic devices involved in aerospace systems and it is typically carried out following a two-stage approach: acquisition and tracking. The first stage detects the presence of the desired signal

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and provides a coarse estimate of its synchronization parameters, and the second one refines those estimates, filtering out noise and tracking any possible time-variation [1]. In the present work, we are concerned with the analysis of the carrier phase (CP) tracking problem. Hence acquisition and time-delay synchronization are not discussed.

Digital CP tracking techniques implemented in conventional receivers rely on well known phaselocked loop (PLL) architectures [2]–[4], that set an output signal's phase relative to an input reference signal's phase. Those circuits are widely used in positioning systems, communications, computers, control, and measurement applications for frequency synthesis, clock and data recovery, clock distribution, and other more specialized functions. The signals of interest may be any periodic waveform, but are typically sinusoids or digital clocks.

Digital PLLs can be implemented in hardware (usually with mixed signal or all-digital integrated circuits in CMOS technology [5]–[7], and targeting frequencies on the order of GHz and above [8]), but the rapid evolution of programmable devices such as field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), digital signal processors (DSPs), microcontrollers and general purpose processors (GPPs) enables software-defined implementations targeting frequencies up to the hundreds of MHz, in which the designer trades electronic components for computation resources [9], [10]. This approach provides advantages such as easy customization of the feedback loop and a drastic reduction in the development cost when compared to the hardware counterpart. However, the underlying design principles remain the same regardless of the technology of choice for the implementation.

The performance obtained with those techniques is generally good enough in benign propagation conditions, but they have been shown to deliver poor estimates or even fail under harsh propagation environments, where the signal may be affected by high dynamics, shadowing, strong fading, multipath effects or ionospheric scintillation [11], [12]. On the basis of conventional PLL architectures, some improvements have been proposed in the literature [13]–[15], but their performance have been overcome by KF-based techniques [11], [12], [16]–[18]. The main drawback of KFs is the need of an exact knowledge of the system model noise statistics' for an optimal behavior, thus being constraint by the accuracy of the dynamic model and the *a priori* fixed system parameters. In practice, those quantities may need to be somehow adjusted to provide a robust solution [19], a problem which has been solved by the so-called adaptive KFs (AKFs) [19]–[24].

Our previous experience on the use of KF synchronization schemes for both communications [25], [26] and positioning systems [19], [27]–[29], and the lack of a unified analysis in the literature and a clear answer to the PLL vs KF dilemma ignited this work. From different analysis carried out in the literature for specific scenarios, it seems clear that KF schemes should in general be preferred in front of PLL-based solutions, but the synchronization and aerospace communities seem still reluctant to go further on theoretical analysis of such techniques and to cross the gap between theory and implementation. Moreover, the advent of software defined radio (SDR) receivers in real-life applications [30], [31] has confirmed the practical feasibility of this approach. The main goal of this tutorial-style paper is to provide a comprehensive overview and unified framework. Therefore, this work is addressed to both the practitioner or engineer who needs to solve real hands-on problems and the academic or researcher willing to push forward on new advanced synchronization techniques.

The notation used along this paper is as follows: lowercase italics for scalar variables, either deterministic or stochastic, both real or complex; uppercase italics for constants; lowercase bold for vector variables, column-wise defined; uppercase bold for matrix variables; $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^*$, and $(\cdot)^H$ stand for the transpose, conjugate, and conjugate transpose (hermitic) operators, respectively; $\hat{x}_{k|k-1}$ is an

estimate of the true parameter value x at time k , given its value in time $k - 1$; $x \sim N(\mu_x, \sigma_x^2)$ is a random variable x Gaussian-distributed with mean μ_x and variance σ_x^2 ; and $\Re(x)$ and $\Im(x)$ stand for the real and imaginary parts of x , respectively. More notation will be defined throughout the paper as needed.

The remainder of this paper is organized in the following way: Section II describes carrier phase synchronization architectures based on PLLs, along with their design principles and trade-offs; Section III reviews the KF-based approach, its variants and practical implementation issues; Section IV compares both approaches and establishes some parallels and equivalences between them; Section V describes advanced KF-based approaches, and Section VI presents computer simulations of practical schemes supporting the presented theoretical corpus. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. PLL-BASED ARCHITECTURES

CP synchronization techniques implemented during the last decades in mass-market and industrial-grade positioning, communications and tracking systems receivers rely on well-established PLL-based architectures [4], [32], [33]. Firstly analyzed by Appleton in 1922 [34], early applications of PLLs were the control of receivers' local oscillators, specially in FM demodulators, and automatic volume control circuits. In the early 1950s, they played an important role in the development of color television [35], and the availability of PLL integrated circuits in the mid-1960s facilitated their rapid introduction into a wide range of consumer products, becoming a key component of electronic devices for the next three decades [36]–[38]. Nowadays, digital PLLs are widely used in modern communication systems [39] and are still the method of choice in many applications such as Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) [3] and space communications [40], mainly because of manufacturers inertia on legacy solutions and well-proven technologies. Hereafter, the main PLL-based architectures and design rules are summarized.

A. Basics

In general, a PLL is built up with three main blocks: the discriminator or phase detector, the loop filter and a numerically controlled oscillator (NCO), which is nothing but an integrator. The main idea is to obtain first an error signal (*i.e.*, discriminator's output), which is proportional to the CP error; then this error goes through the loop filter, in charge of filtering out noise and driving the error to zero; and finally, the NCO is used to generate the local replica (*i.e.*, a complex exponential using the predicted/tracked CP). The basic PLL architecture is sketched in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Standard PLL architecture.

The role of the phase discriminator is to produce an output which is proportional to the phase estimation error. In the presence of data modulating the phase of the input signal (and thus producing phase jumps), *non-coherent* discriminators (usually known as Costas-type discriminators) should be adopted. The two quadrant arctangent discriminator ($\text{atan}(=y_k)/\langle y_k \rangle$) is usually the preferred noncoherent choice [3], although other discriminators may result from different optimization criteria and SNR regimes [41], [42]. Otherwise, if phase jumps produced by data have been removed (either because they belong to a training sequence known at the receiver, or because they have been estimated), or pilot (dataless) signals are available, *coherent* discriminators may be used [39]. In the absence of data, the optimal maximum likelihood (ML) estimator is the four quadrant arctangent

discriminator ($\text{atan2}(\langle y_k \rangle, \langle \dot{y}_k \rangle)$). Additionally to the phase discriminators, one may be interested in directly tracking the input signal frequency using a frequency locked loop (FLL). Refer to [43] for a detailed analysis and updated overview on carrier tracking techniques.

The order of the PLL refers to the overall closed loop (which is used throughout the paper to unify the notation) and not only to the filter loop, which may lead to confusion because the latter is always one order lower than the entire loop due to the NCO. The order of the PLL basically determines the input signal dynamics that the filter is able to track. In other words, a 2nd order PLL is able to track a constant frequency mismatch, whereas a 3rd order PLLs properly tracks frequency drifts. The loop coefficients are usually optimized to minimize the MSE [3] but other approaches may be adopted as well [44].

The dynamics of a PLL are heavily dependent on the type and response of the loop filters. A PLL with n -th order filter is of $(n + 1)$ -th order. In the general case, a PLL of order n has a closed-loop transfer function that can be expressed as [45]:

$$H(s) = H_{PI}(s)L(s) \quad (1)$$

where $H_{PI}(s) = K_1 + \frac{K_2}{s} + \frac{K_3}{s^2} + \dots$ is the transfer function of the proportional plus integrator part,

K_i is the gain of the loop of order i , and $L(s)$ is the transfer function of the loop filter.

B. Analog vs Digital

To start from the scratch and see how digital PLLs are derived from their analog design, some results on analog PLLs are given together with their digital counterpart.

1) *Analog PLLs*: the Laplace transform of the continuous time domain transfer functions for the 2nd and 3rd order PLL loop filters are, respectively,

$$L_2(s) = \frac{a\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}{s} ; L_3(s) = \frac{c\omega_n s^2 + b\omega_n^2 s + \omega_n^3}{s^2}, \quad (2)$$

where a , b and c are the loop filter coefficients, and ω_n (rad/s) is the so-called natural frequency of the loop filter. The PLL loop is closed with a voltage controlled oscillator (VCO), with transfer function $V(s) = 1/s$ (unity VCO gain). The closed-loop transfer functions for these 2nd and 3rd order PLLs are:

$$H_2(s) = \frac{a\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}{s^2 + a\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}, \quad (3)$$

$$H_3(s) = \frac{c\omega_n s^2 + b\omega_n^2 s + \omega_n^3}{s^3 + c\omega_n s^2 + b\omega_n^2 s + \omega_n^3}. \quad (4)$$

The single-sided loop noise bandwidth B_n in Hz (defined as the bandwidth of a perfect rectangular filter which produces the same integrated noise power as that of the actual filter) is obtained from the

frequency response (setting $s = j2\pi f$) of the closed-loop system as

$$B_{n,i} = \int_0^\infty |H_i(j2\pi f)|^2 df, \quad (5)$$

where i is the loop order. This bandwidth can be used to compute the receiver's noise floor (kTB_n) and its sensitivity (the minimum input signal power required to produce a specified signal-to-noise ratio at the receiver's output). Eq. (5) can be analytically computed from the

loop parameters and the natural frequency [3]. Again, considering the 2nd and 3rd order loops, the noise bandwidth can be written as:

$$B_{n,2} = \left(\frac{a^2 + 1}{4a^2} \right) \omega_n ; B_{n,3} = \left(\frac{bc^2 + (b^2 - c)}{4(bc - 1)} \right) \omega_n \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the design of the analog PLL is completely specified by the desired noise bandwidth and the filter parameters, which are usually designed to minimize the estimation's MSE. Typical values

are [3]: $a = \sqrt{2}$, $b = 1.1$ and $c = 2.4$, which is the setup used in the literature to compute the PLL parameters from a specified noise bandwidth.

2) *Digital PLLs*: digital PLLs are usually derived from their analog counterpart. Using $s = (1 - z^{-1})/T_s$, with T_s the sampling period, one can obtain the PLL loop transfer function and the overall closed-loop transfer function. In this case, the VCO is replaced by a NCO with transfer function

$$N(z) = \frac{z^{-1}}{1 - z^{-1}} \quad (7)$$

Considering the following loop filter transfer functions [15]

$$L_2(z) = \alpha_1 + \frac{\alpha_2}{1 - z^{-1}}, \quad (8)$$

$$L_3(z) = \alpha_1 + \frac{\alpha_2}{1 - z^{-1}} + \frac{\alpha_3}{(1 - z^{-1})^2}, \quad (9)$$

the discrete-time closed-loop transfer function for the 2nd and 3rd order PLLs are

$$H_2(z) = \frac{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)z - \alpha_1}{(z - 1)^2 + \alpha_1(z - 1) + \alpha_2 z}, \quad (10)$$

$$H_3(z) = \frac{\alpha_2}{(z - 1)^3 + \alpha_1(z - 1)^2 + \alpha_2 z(z - 1) + \alpha_3 z^2}, \quad (11)$$

where the loop filter coefficients can be directly computed from the analog loop filter parameters, the desired noise bandwidth and the sampling period as

- 2nd order: $\alpha_1 = a\omega_n T_s$ and $\alpha_2 = \omega_n T_s^2$.
- 3rd order: $\alpha_1 = c\omega_n T_s$, $\alpha_2 = b\omega_n T_s^2$ and $\alpha_3 = \omega_n T_s^3$.

For the digital PLL, the equivalent noise bandwidth can be directly computed from $H(z)$ (results given in Hz) [15], leading to

$$B_{n,2} = \frac{2\alpha_1^2 + 2\alpha_2 + \alpha_1\alpha_2}{2T_s\alpha_1(4 - 2\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}, \quad (12)$$

$$B_{n,3} = \frac{\gamma_{3,1}}{2T_s\gamma_{3,2}\gamma_{3,3}}. \quad (13)$$

with $\gamma_{3,1} = 4\alpha_1\alpha_2 - 4\alpha_1\alpha_3 + 4\alpha_2^2 + 2\alpha_1\alpha_2 + 4\alpha_1\alpha_3 + 4\alpha_2\alpha_3 + 3\alpha_1\alpha_2\alpha_3 + \alpha_3^2 + \alpha_1\alpha_3^2$, $\gamma_{3,2} = \alpha_1\alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_1\alpha_3$ and $\gamma_{3,3} = 8 - 4\alpha_1 - 2\alpha_2 - \alpha_3$.

These results verify that digital PLL parameters computed from the analog coefficients are equivalent to the parameters directly derived in the discrete-time domain, since the resulting equivalent noise bandwidths coincide.

C. Standard and Advanced PLLs

A key step for the practitioner may be how to interpret (8) or (9), and the way to turn them into a useful architecture. The block diagram of a 3rd order PLL loop filter is sketched in Figure 2. The

Fig. 2. Block diagram of a 3rd order digital PLL loop filter.

standard PLL-based architectures are somehow limited because of the noise reduction vs. dynamic range tradeoff, which may lead the filters to lose lock.

This tradeoff is mainly driven by the bandwidth and order of the loop. A small bandwidth is needed to filter out as much noise as possible to be able to operate at low SNR, whereas a large one is required for coping with fast variations of the parameters of interest. Moreover, loop's order also plays an important role in such scenarios. For instance, the 2nd order PLL is unconditionally stable at all noise bandwidths but it is not suitable to deal with complex dynamics. The 3rd order PLL, while being more flexible in front of high dynamics, only remains stable for bandwidths below 18 Hz [3]. Another issue is the PLL constant bandwidth, *a priori* fixed by the designer. A time-varying bandwidth would seem to be more suitable in practice. These two key points have led to propose a plethora of advanced PLL-based techniques.

One possible solution to provide robustness and extra flexibility to the standalone PLLs is to consider *cooperative loops architectures*, where several loops interact to counteract its individual limitations. The most basic solution is the so-called *switching architecture*, where a PLL is used under nominal operation but the system switches to a FLL in harsh conditions to not lose lock [46]. The FLL is in general more robust than the PLL because the variability of the incoming signal frequency is orders of magnitude lower than the phase variability. But the solution usually adopted to overcome the problems of standard architectures in dynamic or harsh conditions is the use of a hybrid approach where a FLL permanently assists a PLL (F-PLL) [13], [47], which is capable to maintain lock in situations where the PLL diverges. The second concern that typically arises from standard architectures is the constant bandwidth operation, which may limit its applicability to rather constant propagation conditions. A possible solution is to directly use the input working conditions to automatically adjust the loop bandwidth, what is usually known as *adaptive bandwidth PLL* (A-PLL) [48]. Several contributions appeared in the literature using the same concept [15], [49], [50].

The following section presents a systematic, unified approach to design digital phase tracking filters that is based on the technically sound Bayesian filtering theory.

III. STANDARD KF-BASED CARRIER TRACKING

A. Optimal filtering background and KF general formulation

The optimal filtering problem involves the recursive (i.e., on-line) estimation of time-varying unknown states of a system using the incoming flow of information (observations) from the system, along some prior statistical knowledge about the variations of such states. The general dynamic state-space model (assuming additive noises) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{f}_{k-1}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}) + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{n}_k, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ are the hidden states of the system and measurements at time k , $\mathbf{f}_{k-1}(\cdot)$ and $\mathbf{h}_k(\cdot)$ are known, possibly nonlinear functions; v_k and \mathbf{n}_k are referred to as process and measurement noises (assumed mutually independent stochastic processes). The optimal Bayesian filtering solution [51] is given by the marginal distribution $p(\mathbf{x}_k|\mathbf{y}_{1:k})^1$, which gathers all the information about the system contained in the available observations. This distribution can be recursively computed in two steps: i) *prediction*: the predictive distribution $p(\mathbf{x}_k|\mathbf{y}_{1:k-1})$ is computed using prior information, $p(\mathbf{x}_k|\mathbf{x}_{k-1})$, and the previous distribution, and, ii) *update*: the new measurements \mathbf{y}_k and the predictive distribution are used to obtain the new filtering distribution, $p(\mathbf{x}_k|\mathbf{y}_{1:k})$ (see Algorithm 1 in [53])

The standard KF [51], sketched in Algorithm 1², provides the closed form solution to the optimal Bayesian filtering problem in linear/Gaussian systems, assumptions that not always hold. A plethora of alternatives have been proposed in the last decades to solve the nonlinear estimation problem. Among them are the extended KF (EKF) [51], the family of sigma point KFs [54] within the Gaussian framework, and the family of Sequential Monte Carlo methods [55] for arbitrary noise distributions. The carrier synchronization problem is just a particular application case of such general filtering solution.

The probabilistic assumptions made by the KF are $v_k \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_k)$ and $\mathbf{n}_k \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_k)$, with \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{R}_k being the process and measurement covariance matrices, respectively. For linear dynamic systems the KF always provides the linear MMSE solution, but if the process or measurement noises are not Gaussian distributed, the KF is no longer optimal. The filter uses a Gaussian approximation, and only propagates the mean and covariance of the predictive and posterior distributions, so intuitively *the further from Gaussianity, the further from optimality*.

The filtering equation in step 7 of Algorithm 1 reveals how the KF estimation works:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k|k} = \underbrace{\mathbf{F}_{k-1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}}_{\text{state prediction}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{k|k-1})}_{\text{measurement update}}. \quad (16)$$

Algorithm 1 General Kalman filter formulation

Require: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$, $\mathbf{P}_{x,0|0}$, \mathbf{F}_k , \mathbf{H}_k , \mathbf{y}_k , \mathbf{Q}_k and $\mathbf{R}_k \forall k$

1: Set $k \leftarrow 1$

Time update (prediction)

2: Estimate the predicted state: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}_{k-1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1|k-1}$, 3:

Estimate the predicted error covariance:

$$\mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}_{k-1} \mathbf{P}_{x,k-1|k-1} \mathbf{F}_{k-1}^\top + \mathbf{Q}_k.$$

Measurement update (estimation)

4: Estimate the predicted measurement: $\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{k|k-1} = \mathbf{H}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k|k-1}$.

5: Estimate the innovation covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{P}_{y,k|k-1} = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top + \mathbf{R}_k.$$

6: Estimate the Kalman gain: $\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top \mathbf{P}_{y,k|k-1}^{-1}$.

7: Estimate the updated state: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k|k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}^{k|k-1})$.

8: Estimate the corresponding error covariance:

$$\mathbf{P}_{x,k|k} = \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1}.$$

9: Set $k \leftarrow k + 1$ and go to step 2.

¹

²

The first term takes into account the state evolution model to predict the state at the following time step, while the second one corrects this prediction by incorporating the information provided by the new measurement, \mathbf{y}_k . The term $\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{k|k-1}$ is called *innovation*, which can be seen as an error signal and a key part of the KF theory. If the filter is optimal, the innovations' sequence is a white Gaussian process, which is a useful theoretical result to build consistency tests [56], [57].

The innovations are weighted by the time-varying Kalman gain, \mathbf{K}_k , which is computed using the uncertainty of the state-space model (i.e., noise statistics) and the covariance of the estimation error (i.e., how good the state estimation is),

$$\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top (\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top + \mathbf{R}_k)^{-1}. \tag{17}$$

Observing the terms involved in the gain computation, and with a slight abuse of language, the following effects can be deduced: *i)* increasing the measurement noise, \mathbf{R}_k , or equivalently the uncertainty on the observation, reduces \mathbf{K}_k and thus the filter is less confident on the information provided by the observations; *ii)* on the other side, increasing the system model uncertainty, \mathbf{Q}_k , increases $\mathbf{P}_{x,k|k-1}$ and in turn \mathbf{K}_k . In this situation, more weight is given to the observations and less to the state prediction. If the system is *observable* (i.e., the system states can be changed by changing the system input) and *controllable* (i.e., the value of the initial state can be determined from the system output) the filter tends to an asymptotic regime [58], that is, both \mathbf{K}_k and the estimation error covariance matrix tend to steady-state fixed values,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{K}_k \rightarrow \mathbf{K}_\infty; \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{P}_{x,k|k} \rightarrow \mathbf{P}_\infty. \tag{18}$$

These values only depend on the transition matrices and both process and measurement noise statistics, thus can be computed off-line. The steady-state error covariance is obtained by solving a discrete algebraic Riccati equation, and the steady-state gain is straightforwardly derived from this covariance matrix. The use of such constant gain may be really useful in applications where computational

Fig. 3. Linear KF-based carrier tracking architecture with noisy carrier observations.

complexity is a very critical point, since a steady-state convergence ensures that the gain in Equation (16) does not need to be recomputed at each time instant (that is, $\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{K}_\infty$). In this case, it is worth to take into account that during the transient time the filter is no longer optimal, and the Riccati equation may not converge [59].

The KF formulation is only valid for linear systems but in many real-life applications the measurement function, the state evolution, or both may be nonlinear. A classical solution is to use the so-called EKF, which uses a linearization of such nonlinear functions and directly

applies the KF equations. The key point is to use linearized transition matrices (Jacobian matrices) such as³

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{k-1} = \nabla \mathbf{f}_{k-1}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1})|_{\mathbf{x}_{k-1}^{k-1}}; \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k = \nabla \mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_k)|_{\mathbf{x}_k^{k-1}},$$

and plug them into steps 3, 5, and 7 of Algorithm 1. Notice that in steps 2 and 4 we can use nonlinear functions. It is out of the scope to provide a detailed discussion on KF theory, for further details on the topic refer to [51], [60].

B. Carrier tracking state-space formulation

Is usually assumed that the phase variations of the signal of interest are due either to the relative movement between the transmitter and the receiver or to synchronization mismatches, and on top of it there is a random behavior due to the noises affecting the system. The state-space formulation of this problem is defined via both process and measurement equations, as shown hereafter.

1) *Carrier tracking process equation:*

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{F}_{k-1}\mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \mathbf{v}_k, \tag{19}$$

where the additive noise includes any possible modeling mismatch; the state to be tracked includes the CP and the Doppler frequency terms (i.e., using a Taylor series expansion of the CP and truncating at the order of interest); and the so-called transition matrix, \mathbf{F}_{k-1} , defines the phase evolution due to receiver dynamics. For instance, assuming that tracking phase, θ_k (rad), Doppler shift, f_k (Hz), and Doppler frequency rate, \dot{f}_k (Hz/s), is enough for a given application (i.e., assuming a third order Taylor approximation of the phase), the phase is

$$\theta_k = \theta_0 + 2\pi \left(f_k k T_s + \frac{1}{2} \dot{f}_k k^2 T_s^2 \right), \tag{20}$$

where k refers to the discrete-time instants and T_s is the sampling period. In this scenario, the state

to be tracked is $\mathbf{x}_k = [\theta_k, f_k, \dot{f}_k]^T$ and the transition matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{k-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & T_s & T_s^2/2 \\ 0 & 1 & T_s \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{21}$$

where the phase is expressed in cycles ([rad/2π]). It is straightforward to extend this state formulation to higher order frequency terms if needed.

2) *Carrier tracking observation equation*: two cases may be considered, i) the measurements are noisy *CP observables* (linear equivalent model), and ii) the observations are directly the received signal *baseband complex samples*.

- *Linear observation equation*: the inputs to the carrier tracking block are linearly related to carrier observables,

$$\mathbf{y}^{klin} = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{n}_{\theta,k} \rightarrow y^{klin} = \theta_k + n_{\theta,k}, \tag{22}$$

with \mathbf{H}_k the measurement transition matrix and \mathbf{n}_k the measurement noise including thermal and phase noise contributions, as well as other propagation disturbances.

- *Nonlinear observation equation*: the inputs to the carrier tracking block are the complex baseband signal samples, which are nonlinearly related to the carrier observables,

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{n}_k \rightarrow y_k = \gamma_k e^{j\theta_k} + n_k, \tag{23}$$

with $\mathbf{h}_k(\cdot)$ the nonlinear measurement function, and γ_k refers to the time-varying envelope of the received signal, which may be affected by different propagation disturbances such as fading, multipath or scintillation.

Early approaches to this problem, such as the α - β and the α - β - γ filters [61], do not require a detailed system model, trading computational load by a degradation in performance with respect to the KF [62] due to their static, heuristically chosen gains.

C. KF-based carrier synchronization architectures

In this section, different architectures to implement the KF-based carrier tracking solution are provided, coupling the general formulation given in Section III-A with the specific state-space model of Section III-B [16], [25].

Fig. 4. Standard (top) and Extended (bottom) KF-based carrier tracking architectures. The standard KF uses a discriminator as a phase detector, while the EKF directly operates with the input complex samples and computes $\mathbf{P}_{y,k|k-1}$, \mathbf{K}_k and $\mathbf{P}_{x,k|k}$ using the linearized $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k$.

- 1) *Linear observation architectures*: the inputs to the tracking block are directly phase observables, thus using the state-space model defined by (19) and (22). Note that this

architecture is called *standard linear KF* throughout the paper, but in the literature it is also referred to as *direct-state KF* [16]. The closed-loop block diagram is sketched in Fig. 3. An alternative linear architecture named *error-state KF* or rate-only feedback loop, which is typically used in GNSS [63], [64], is presented and analyzed in [16] with respect to the standard (direct-state) KF. The idea consists of using a state-space model where the filter does not track directly the CP but the phase error. As it does not provide any advantage over the standard KF, the latter is preferred for practical applications.

2) *Nonlinear observation architectures*: the previous linear architecture is of limited applicability in real-life implementations. At least, some extra information should be added to explain how the phase observables are obtained. The standard solution is to use a discriminator, as done in traditional PLL architectures (Case I), but the complex samples of the received baseband signal can be directly treated using a nonlinear filter (Case II).

- Case I - Discriminator-based traditional approach:

Using a discriminator allows to use a traditional KF and avoids the derivation of suboptimal solutions, and is considered the reference KF-based architecture [43]. The main differences with the linear standard KF are *i*) the carrier generator block, which uses the nonlinear observation equation, $\mathbf{h}_k(\cdot)$, and *ii*) the discriminator as phase detector. The block diagram is shown in Figure

4 (top).

- Case II - Extended KF solution:

Using a discriminator might break the Gaussianity assumption within the KF, making the filter not optimal anymore, which may lead to poor filter performances or even divergence. Moreover, the discriminators may need to operate under saturation in low SNR scenarios. A solution is to directly deal with the nonlinear Gaussian observation model [25], [26]. The simplest solution is to use a linearization procedure (EKF-like solution) and then re-use the previous linear standard KF approach, sketched in the bottom diagram of Figure 4.

In practice, there are some issues which are of capital importance for the actual implementation,

detailed hereafter.

D. On the implementation issues

1) *Noise statistics*: it is common for the system model not to be perfectly known, and thus the noise covariance matrices are set to some expected value. A rule of thumb typically considered in the KF design is that *noise covariances must be equal or greater than the true ones to ensure the filter convergence*. Therefore it is convenient to be rather conservative and do not underestimate the noise impact into the system. If $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_k > \mathbf{Q}_k^4$, the steady-state filter performance may be worse but the filter tends to be more reactive and robust to model changes, so more suitable to rapidly time-varying scenarios. Regarding the measurement noise, $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_k > \mathbf{R}_k$ implies that $\mathbf{K}_k < \mathbf{K}_{optimal}$, and thus the filter relies more on the process transition model [19].

An expression for the approximated variance of the phase noise, expressed in squared-radians, at the output of the Costas-type two quadrant arctangent discriminator is [65]:

$$\sigma_{n_\theta}^2 = \frac{1}{2C/N_0T_s} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2C/N_0T_s} \right) \quad (24)$$

⁴ $\mathbf{A} > \mathbf{B}$ means that $\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}$ is non-negative definite [60].

where C/N_0 is the carrier to noise density ratio (independent of the receiver bandwidth, B_w), which is related to the SNR as

$$C/N_0(\text{dB-Hz}) = \text{SNR (dB)} + 10\log_{10}(B_w(\text{Hz})). \tag{25}$$

The process noise covariance matrix is fixed according to the expected dynamic working conditions. Considering the 3rd order illustrative example, this covariance is related to the frequency rate error variance (i.e., possible frequency rate modeling error or higher order expected dynamics).

2) *Filter initialization:* how to set the initial values is something completely application-dependent. In practice, the best option is to set these parameters according to some *a priori* information or physical meaning. Taking into account the example at hand, where the state to be tracked is $\mathbf{x}_k = [\hat{\theta}_k; \hat{f}_k; \hat{f}'_k]$,

Fig. 5. Standard 2nd order PLL vs standard two-states ($\mathbf{x}_k = [\theta_k f_k]$) KF.

the initial values can be set to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = [0; 0; 0]$. The initial error covariance is defined as

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{x},0|0} = \text{diag}(\sigma_{\theta_0}^2, \sigma_{f_0}^2, \sigma_{f'_0}^2),$$

where the initial phase error variance can be set to $\sigma_{\theta_0}^2 = \pi^2/3$ (rad²) if the initial phase is uniform in $[-\pi, \pi]$, or equal to $\sigma_{\theta_0}^2 = 1/12$ (cycles²) if it is considered in $[-1/2, 1/2]$. The initial frequency and frequency rate error variances depend on the acquisition stage. The maximum expected acquisition error or acquisition resolution determines the maximum expected initial tracking frequency error.

IV. PLL VS KF ARCHITECTURE COMPARISON

In the previous sections, the basics of both PLL and KF-based carrier tracking architectures have been introduced in a separate manner. Regarding the problem at hand, some comparisons between PLLs and KFs are found in the literature, but only taking into account basic architectures. This section provides a comparison of those two approaches, not only for conventional architectures but also for most advanced PLL-based solutions.

A. Conventional PLL vs standard KF

The fact that a 2nd order PLL is equivalent to a 2nd order KF in steady-state conditions (i.e., for a time-invariant system with an a priori fixed Kalman gain) is well known [66].

Recently, the equivalence between both techniques in steady-state conditions has been shown for the 3rd order case [67]. A block diagram comparison is sketched in Figure 5 reusing the previously introduced standard architectures, where it is easy to identify the block-by-block equivalence. In the KF approach, the innovations' sequence goes through the discriminator to obtain the residual phase error to be used in the linear KF implementation, as in the PLL. Then, the estimated phase is constructed from the weighted residual error plus the predicted value, being directly the implementation of the KF equations. Notice that, in both cases, the input to the carrier generator block is the predicted phase, and therefore the equivalence is made more evident if the KF formulation is expressed in the predictor form,

$$\mathbf{x}^{\wedge}_{k+1|k} = \mathbf{F}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{k|k-1}). \tag{26}$$

Considering the phase contribution (i.e., the first element of \mathbf{x}_k) and the linear 2nd order loop form, this equation can be rewritten as:

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\theta}_{k|k-1} + T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \underbrace{\left(\alpha_{1,k} + \frac{\alpha_{2,k}}{T_s} \right)}_{\substack{\text{Output of the loop} \\ \text{Equivalent to NCO}}} \epsilon_k \tag{27}$$

with $\mathbf{K}_k = [\alpha_{1,k} \ \alpha_{2,k}]^>$ and ϵ_k representing the KF discriminator output, and where the main architectural contributions have been identified to construct the parallelism with the standard PLL architecture.

The predicted phase in a standard 2nd order PLL is

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1}^{PLL} = \hat{\theta}_k^{PLL} + (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)\epsilon_k + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \alpha_2 \epsilon_i \tag{28}$$

It is straightforward from this expression (see Figure 5) and the NCO expression in (7) to see that the

2nd order joint PLL loop filter plus NCO operation can be written using a state-space formulation as

[16]:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^{PLL} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & T_s \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^{PLL} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & T_s \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \frac{\alpha_2}{T_s} \end{pmatrix} \epsilon_k, \tag{29}$$

with ϵ_k the PLL discriminator output in cycles and $\mathbf{x}^{\wedge}_{k|k} = [\hat{\theta}_k \ \hat{f}_k]^>$, which is strictly equivalent to the KF considering constant gains (i.e., notice the effect of the state prediction matrix \mathbf{F}_k , which implies a modification of the original gain α_2). By considering frequency estimates at the output of the loop filter and a first order NCO, the standard loop filter and NCO block structure is recovered from (29), as shown in (27). The equivalence for the 3rd order PLL is straightforward considering the carrier tracking state-space formulation example in Section III-B. Again, a difference between both gains must be commented: if the standard PLL implementation has a set of 3 coefficients equal to $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$, the strictly equivalent KF must consider the following constant gains due to the effect of the transition matrix (i.e., phase expressed in cycles),

$$\mathbf{K} = [\alpha_1 \alpha_2/T_s \ 2\alpha_3/T_s^2]_>$$

This subtle adjustment leads to the following equation (with $\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2/T_s + 2\alpha_3/T_s^2$):

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\theta}_{k|k-1} + T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \frac{T_s^2 \hat{\dot{f}}_{k|k-1}}{2} + \alpha \epsilon_k,$$

where the different gains in the Doppler frequency and Doppler frequency rate terms, $T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1}$ and $T_s^2 \hat{\dot{f}}_{k|k-1}/2$, naturally appear in the standard PLL predicted phase expression when considering the corresponding loop gains \mathbf{K} and the PLL state-space formulation (as in (29)).

From an architectural point of view, there is a clear parallelism between the well-known PLL and the standard KF formulation. The main difference is that the loop filter gain is somehow heuristically adjusted in the PLL but optimally computed in the KF. If the system is time-invariant and the PLL bandwidth is set according to the expected actual working conditions, this heuristic adjustment may not be an inconvenience. In this case, the Kalman gain tends rapidly to its steady-state value, \mathbf{K}_∞ . But the flexibility of the KF optimal gain plays an important role in real-life time-varying scenarios, where the optimal gain does not tend to a steady-state value but evolves with time. Therefore, the PLL is a simplified particular case of the general KF.

The following 1-sigma equation is typically used to determine the desired (“optimal”) static PLL loop bandwidth,

$$\underbrace{\sigma_{noise}(B_w)}_{\text{measurement noise dynamics}} + \underbrace{\frac{\theta_e(B_w)}{3}}_{\text{dynamic stress}} \leq \text{threshold} \rightarrow B_{opt}, \quad (30)$$

where the predefined threshold is usually known as *loss-of-lock threshold*. This threshold is typically set to 1/12 of the pull-in range of the discriminator, that is, 30° (coherent) and 15° (non-coherent). Considering an arctangent Costas discriminator, the thermal noise jitter contribution is

$$\sigma_{noise} = \sqrt{\frac{B_w}{C/N_0} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2C/N_0 T_s}\right)} \quad (\text{rad}), \quad (31)$$

and the dynamic stress, θ_e , is related to the maximum line-of-sight (LOS) expected phase dynamics [3]. For instance, in a 2nd order PLL the phase model considers a constant Doppler shift, thus the dynamic stress is the maximum LOS acceleration. In a 3rd order PLL, the filter tracks a Doppler shift and Doppler frequency rate, then the dynamic stress is the maximum LOS jerk.

B. Cooperative loops vs KF joint estimation

The noise reduction versus dynamic range tradeoff introduced in Section II, which is the main problematic of standard constant-bandwidth standalone PLLs, is clear from (30): if the noise affecting the system ($\sigma_{noise}(B_w)$) increases, in order to maintain the jitter below the threshold one must lower the loop bandwidth for an optimal behavior. But if the system dynamics ($\theta_e(B_w)$) increase, one must increase the loop bandwidth, which is inversely related to the dynamic stress.

In practice, the loop bandwidth is set to the minimum value that is able to cope with the maximum expected dynamics, which is suboptimal most of the time. A well-established solution to cope with this trade-off under non-nominal propagation conditions is the use of cooperative loops. A popular approach is the F-PLL [47], which uses a FLL to permanently assist a PLL and thus providing a

Fig. 6. FLL-assisted PLL (F-PLL) loop architecture block diagram.

frequency aiding. The key idea directly arises from the bandwidth determination using (30). If one is capable to reduce as much as possible the dynamic stress of the loop, then a much lower loop bandwidth may be used to cope with low SNR scenarios. Under these circumstances, the main filter only copes with the residual frequency errors and focuses on noise reduction. The classic 2nd order FLL-assisted 3rd order PLL architectures is sketched in Figure 6 [47], where the FLL loop structure is preserved to give a clear picture of the corresponding frequency aiding interaction with the PLL. It is important to point out that both the FLL and PLL bandwidths are heuristically adjusted, relying on the correct operation of the frequency aiding provided by the FLL.

In the literature, a comparison between the F-PLL and the KF at a theoretical level or looking for the architectural equivalence, as done for the standard PLL, does not exist as far as authors' knowledge. Using the state-space formulation for the PLL introduced in (29), and considering that the FLL tracks $[f_k \dot{f}_k]$, the interaction between both filters is expressed as:

$$\rho_k^{FLL} = \hat{f}_{k|k-1}^{FLL} + (\beta_1 + \beta_2)e_{f,k}, \tag{32}$$

with β_1 and β_2 the FLL gains and $e_{f,k}$ the frequency discriminator output. Using an equivalent 3rd order PLL state-space model and the frequency aiding, the output of the PLL loop filter is:

$$\rho_k^{PLL} = \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \underbrace{\hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \rho_k^{FLL}}_{\text{Frequency aiding}} + (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3)e_{\theta,k}, \tag{33}$$

where the frequency aiding of the FLL is done via the estimate of the frequency rate. Optimally,

$\hat{f}_{k|k-1}^{FLL} \rightarrow \dot{f}_k$ and thus the frequency rate that the PLL has to track $f_{k|k-1} \rightarrow 0$. This frequency aiding is made explicit by considering the architecture in Figure 6, but is hidden in the overall expression if considering the conventional compact implementation,

$$\rho_{PLLk} = \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \dot{f}_{k|k-1} + \alpha e_{\theta,k} + \beta e_{f,k}. \tag{34}$$

with $\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3$ and $\beta = \beta_1 + \beta_2$.

Using the knowledge on the equivalence between loops, the most obvious and direct application of KFs to emulate the F-PLL makes use of the same architecture by replacing both PLL and FLL with two cooperative KFs. The first KF would be in charge of $\mathbf{x}_k^{(1)} = [\theta_k \ f_k \ \dot{f}_k]^\top$ and the second one of $\mathbf{x}_k^{(2)} = [f_k \ \dot{f}_k]^\top$, with an interaction between both using the output of the 2nd filter as a frequency input to the first KF.

But from an optimal filtering point of view, this is not necessary because a single filter can optimally solve the estimation problem, that is, sequential estimation of $\mathbf{x}_k = [\theta_k \ f_k \ \dot{f}_k]^\top$ using the available observations up to time k . To obtain a fair comparison, the KF should use both phase and frequency discriminators, and therefore the observation equation should be modified to account for both measurements. The resulting KF predictor form is:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} = \mathbf{F}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{K}_k \begin{bmatrix} r_k^{(1)} \\ r_k^{(2)} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{35}$$

where $r_k^{(1)}$ and $r_k^{(2)}$ are the outputs of the KF phase and frequency discriminators, respectively, and

the Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{1,k} \\ \alpha_{2,k} \\ \alpha_{3,k} \end{bmatrix}$

The corresponding predicted phase is given by

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\theta}_{k|k-1} + T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \alpha_{1,k} r_k^{(1)} + \alpha_{2,k} r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_{3,k} \beta_{1,k} + \beta_{2,k} \tag{36}$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\theta}_{k|k-1} + T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \alpha_{1,k} r_k^{(1)} + \alpha_{2,k} r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_{3,k} \beta_{1,k} + \beta_{2,k} \tag{37}$$

with $\alpha_k = \alpha_{1,k} + T_s \alpha_{2,k} + T_s^2 \alpha_{3,k} / 2$ and $\beta = T_s \beta_1 + T_s^2 \beta_2 / 2$. Analyzing (34) and (37), it is straightforward to see that the F-PLL equivalent is obtained with a time-invariant Kalman gain equal

to

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 \\ \alpha_2 / T_s & \beta_1 / T_s \\ 2\alpha_3 / T_s^2 & 2\beta_2 / T_s^2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{38}$$

which leads to the following final phase prediction:

$$\hat{\theta}_{k+1|k} = \hat{\theta}_{k|k-1} + T_s \hat{f}_{k|k-1} + \alpha_{1,k} r_k^{(1)} + \alpha_{2,k} r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_{3,k} \beta_{1,k} + \beta_{2,k} \tag{39}$$

again with $\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3$ and $\beta = \beta_1 + \beta_2$. This result confirms the expression for the time-invariant equivalent Kalman gain previously introduced, and it is equivalent to the compact F-PLL expression in (34). Notice that the gains in the F-PLL are adjusted heuristically, while the KF sequentially computes the optimal gain and provides the optimal solution to the problem. Therefore, the proposed KF is equivalent to the F-PLL formulation, except for the values of the time-variant coefficients, which in fact are optimally computed and not set to constant values.

One can conclude that this KF-based approach provides an optimal solution to the suboptimal F-PLL implementation.

C. Adaptive PLLs vs KF optimal approach

As already stated in Section II, one of the main limitations of standard PLLs is their constant bandwidth, which is *a priori* fixed by the designer according to the expected working conditions (i.e., typically set using (30)) and of limited applicability in time-varying scenarios. An alternative to counteract this lack of adaptability/flexibility is to incorporate the capability to estimate the actual working conditions (i.e., system noise and dynamic stress), what leads to the adaptive bandwidth PLL (A-PLL) [48], [49]. The parameters used to set the loop bandwidth, σ_{noise} and θ_e , can be sequentially estimated from the input samples and the discriminator output.

The standard KF carrier tracking implementation is usually said to inherently have an adaptive bandwidth, because the Kalman gain is optimally computed taking into account both \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{R}_k . But this is only true if the noise statistics are completely specified (i.e., known $\forall k$). In practice, the measurement noise covariance is set according to the expected SNR and usually does not take into account possible variations, and the process noise covariance is determined according to a single application-dependent scenario. Considering constant noise covariances leads to a constant steady-state Kalman gain, and therefore the optimal adaptive behavior of the KF is lost in the implementation for time-variant systems. Analyzing (30), it is easy to see the analogy between the first left-hand term σ_{noise} and \mathbf{R}_k , and the relation between the dynamic stress and \mathbf{Q}_k . In the KF, the relation between those quantities and the filter bandwidth is computed in an optimal manner, while in the A-PLL is suboptimally computed using pre-defined thresholds. If the noise statistics are not fully *a priori* determined, the solution is to estimate and sequentially adjust them into the filter, which is usually known as AKF [19], [24] (see Section V-A for further details). From a practical architecture point of view:

- *Adaptive PLL vs Optimal KF*: the KF does not need any additional processing to estimate the actual working conditions and to optimally adjust the loop bandwidth, which can be seen as an implementation of an optimized A-PLL.
- *Adaptive PLL vs Adaptive KF*: if the system is partially known, an AKF solution is equivalent to the A-PLL. Both architectures make use of an estimate of the system noise ($\hat{\mathbf{R}}_k$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{noise}$) and the dynamic stress ($\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_k$ and $\hat{\theta}_e$), but the AKF optimally adjusts the loop bandwidth according to these estimates while the A-PLL uses a somehow heuristic threshold-dependent approach.

To conclude, with respect to the A-PLL, both KF-based adaptive approaches will always be superior in terms of performance, optimality and flexibility [11].

V. ADVANCED KF-BASED APPROACHES

In the previous section, the KF-based formulation of standard and advanced PLL architectures has been detailed from both theoretical, architectural and conceptual points of view. The main idea was to show that a standard PLL is a particular suboptimal implementation of the KF, that the cooperative loops can also be formulated using KFs, and that the adaptive bandwidth loops are actually improved when using a KF approach. The goals of this section are first to give a deeper insight on the adaptive KF schemes, and then, to show that the flexibility of the KF goes far beyond the implementation of existing PLL-based architectures, and that much more complex problems, which cannot be treated from a PLL point of view, can actually be solved using powerful KF-based solutions.

A. Adaptive KF tracking schemes

In standard KF-based tracking architectures, both the measurement noise variance, $\sigma_{n,k}^2$, and the process noise covariance matrix, \mathbf{Q}_k , are assumed to be perfectly known, which is not realistic in practical implementations and may lead to poor performances in time-varying scenarios. The concept behind the AKF has already been introduced in the previous section when compared to the adaptive PLL approach. The main goal of the AKF is to sequentially adjust the noise statistics according to the actual working conditions, in order to obtain a robust and reliable tracking solution and to provide the answer to the problem of interest here: variability. This is equivalent to obtain a sequential optimal time-varying Kalman gain adaptation (i.e., adaptive equivalent noise bandwidth). The suboptimality introduced by the lack of precise knowledge of the noise statistics within the KF framework may introduce several estimation errors [68]. Therefore, a real-life robust system must counteract the fact that accurate noise characteristics and dynamic models are hardly available in practice. Two different approaches based on the residuals (state estimate minus prediction) were presented in [20] for vehicle navigation, an adaptive two-stage KF relying on the innovations' covariance is proposed in [21] for high dynamics scenarios, and an ad-hoc implementation called variable gain AKF was introduced in [22]. An interesting alternative approach has been recently presented in [23], [24], where a C/N₀ estimate (which is usually available at the receiver) is used to adjust the carrier phase error variance, which in turn is used to optimally compute the Kalman gain in a time-varying manner.

From an optimal estimation point of view, the problem reduces to the estimation of the covariance matrices of two Gaussian distributions. The carrier tracking problem using standard noise statistics estimation methods [69], [70] was studied in [68], but the problem is not yet solved in a unified manner. In the literature we find a plethora of methods and different approaches to face the noise statistics estimation problem. In the early 70s, Mehra [69] published a survey paper and classified the existing methods into four categories: Bayesian, maximum likelihood (ML), covariance matching and correlation methods. The most popular are the correlation methods [69], and the more recent Autocovariance Least Square (ALS) [71] seems to provide the best solution. A good analysis on the design of such adaptive KFs for carrier tracking is given in [19].

B. Augmented state and multiple models formulations

One of the most important features of the KF-based solution, apart from its optimal approach, is the flexibility it provides to deal with different problems while strictly considering the same architecture, which from a practical point of view may be of capital importance in some applications. For instance, in the carrier tracking problem, to extend a 2nd order loop to a 3rd order one only needs to add the frequency rate into the state evolution formulation, and to extend the corresponding covariance matrices to take it into account. This can be used to include any prior knowledge of the system into the state-space formulation. In some cases, this can be the only way to solve the problem and provide a robust carrier tracking solution. For instance, if some specific propagation conditions are *a priori* known and effectively modeled using a dynamic state-space model, they can be merged together with the carrier phase of interest into a single state-space formulation. In this case, the KF is aware of those specific propagation conditions and may be able to mitigate undesired effects. An illustrative example [28], [29] of a real application of these ideas is presented in Section VI.

All the methods introduced in this paper, from the standard architectures to the most advanced adaptive and augmented state KF-based approaches, rely on a specific dynamic model, which defines the evolution of the parameters of interest (e.g., the carrier phase in this case). The KF is optimal when the state-space formulation perfectly matches the real system. If a mild modeling mismatch or slightly time-varying scenario is considered (i.e., a weak uncertainty about the state evolution, \mathbf{Q}_k , or the measurement noise, \mathbf{R}_k) the natural solution

is given by the AKF, but this approach does not provide a robust solution to strongly time-varying scenarios. High variability in the sense that the system uncertainty is not only on the system noise but on the state-space formulation itself. To overcome this model-based uncertainty, the best solution is to consider model matching/selection strategies. Among the different solutions available in the literature, the most promising is the so-called Interactive Multiple Model (IMM) approach, which has been thoroughly used in target tracking, navigation and high dynamics applications [56], [72]. The main idea behind the IMM is to overcome the main problem of stand-alone KFs following a divide and conquer strategy, dealing with changing scenarios using several easier fixed operation KFs. In other words, it is a bank of interacting KFs running in parallel. Each KF is designed for a specific scenario, and the filter is in charge to construct a final estimate using models' likelihood. Notice that a key point to obtain a good estimate is the interconnection among individual filters. This concept has already been successfully applied to carrier synchronization [27].

VI. COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

To support the discussion on the PLL versus KF dilemma, two illustrative examples of interest to the aerospace community are given in the sequel. The first case deals with the GNSS carrier tracking under harsh propagation conditions, namely considering ionospheric scintillation disturbances, which is a hot topic in the community. The second case proposes a KF-based architecture in a deep space communications system, being an extremely challenging synchronization scenario.

A. Case I: Robust GNSS Carrier Phase Tracking

Ionospheric scintillation is the name given to the disturbance caused by electron density irregularities along the propagation path through the ionosphere. These irregularities affect the GNSS signals with amplitude fades and phase variations. An important feature is the existing correlation between deep amplitude fades and phase variations in a simultaneous random manner, the so-called canonical fades [73]. This is certainly the most challenging scenario in GNSS carrier tracking problems. This particular example is used to support the fact that *prior knowledge on the propagation conditions* can be introduced into the system by *state augmentation*, providing an extra capability to the filter, a fact that is impossible to take into account using PLL-based architectures (see Section V-B).

The scintillation can be modeled as a multiplicative channel [74], $\xi_s(t) = \rho_s(t)e^{j\theta_s(t)}$, and synthesized using the Cornell Scintillation Model (CSM)⁵ [75], where $\rho_s(t)$ and $\theta_s(t)$ are the corresponding envelope and phase components.

The scintillation phase is a correlated stochastic process, which in turn can be fairly modeled as an AR(1) process: $\theta_{s,k} = \beta\theta_{s,k-1} + \eta_k$, with $\eta_k \sim N(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$, which allows to include it into the KF state-space formulation to jointly track the desired phase, $\theta_{d,k}$, Doppler frequency, $f_{d,k}$, frequency rate, $\dot{f}_{d,k}$ and possible scintillation effect, $\theta_{s,k}$. This idea was first introduced in [27] within a multiple model approach, and further extended in [28], [29]. The simplified model for the samples at the input of the carrier tracking stage is

$$y_k = \alpha_k e^{j\theta_k} + n_k; \quad n_k \sim N(0, \sigma_{n,k}^2) \quad (40a)$$

$$\alpha_k = A_k \rho_{s,k}; \quad \theta_k = \theta_{d,k} + \theta_{s,k} \quad (40b)$$

⁵ The CSM has been embedded in the so-called Cornell Scintillation Simulation Matlab toolkit, which is available at <http://gps.ece.cornell.edu/tools.php>. This software will be used in the computer simulations to generate the desired scintillation effect.

where $\rho_{s,k}$ refers to the scintillation amplitude effects. The state evolution [27] is given

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{B} \theta_{d,k} + \mathbf{v}_k \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

where the process noise, $\mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q})$, stands for possible uncertainties or errors on the state transition model.

In this example the signal of interest is corrupted by moderate and severe scintillation, and the following parameters are used: $T_s = 10$ ms, $C/N_0 = 35$ dB-Hz, $f_{d,0} = 2$ Hz and $\dot{f}_{d,0} = 0.1$ Hz/s. The tested methods were: 2nd order PLL ($B_{pll} = 10$ Hz), 2nd order FLL-assisted 3rd order PLL ($B_{pll} = 5$ Hz, $B_{pfl} = 5$ Hz), a standard KF only tracking the dynamics (i.e., $\mathbf{x}^*_k = [\theta_{d,k}, f_{d,k}, \dot{f}_{d,k}]^T$) and a KF including the scintillation into the state-space formulation (termed KF-AR).

The RMSE obtained with the four methods is plotted in Figure 7(a), where it is easy to identify the two regions where the signal is corrupted by scintillation (indicated in the figure). Regarding the performance of the PLL-based techniques and the standard KF, there are two key points that must be stated: i) the standard techniques are unable to identify which phase variations are due to dynamics (desired) and which ones come from the ionospheric scintillation (undesired); ii) if these techniques are well tuned to track fast phase variations (i.e., moderate to high dynamics) or time-varying scenarios, which is a desirable quality of a reliable and robust architecture, will also track the fast scintillation phase variations. The KF-AR provides an increased robustness and better performance. These two statements are more evident in Figure 7(b) and 7(c), where the Doppler frequency and scintillation phase estimation are plotted for a single realization (only available for the KF-based techniques). In the Doppler frequency estimation, one can see that the standard KF understands the scintillation as frequency variations, while the KF-AR correctly decouples both contributions, giving always better performances and being much more robust and powerful.

B. Case II: Signal Tracking in Deep Space Communications

Another example of challenging synchronization is found in deep space communications for planetary exploration, an application with extreme requirements in terms of received low signal power. Synchronization in deep space involves an initial acquisition stage where the PLL is allowed to operate at larger loop bandwidth in order to acquire the carrier frequency in the presence of significant Doppler dynamics. Once the carrier frequency is acquired the receiver enters the tracking stage where the loop bandwidth is typically decreased to reduce the noise in the loop and cope with very low received signal power [40]. Hence, the PLL must be configured to different operating bandwidths that are adapted to the SNR and as well as must cope with loop transitions. Under this scenario the inherent adaptive KF bandwidth and filter flexibility may offer an advantage on loop adaptation/configuration.

This study case considers the following telecommand transmitted (space-to-Earth) signal model known as remnant carrier modulation with sinusoidal subcarrier:

$$s(t) = A \sin(2\pi f_c t + m_c D(t) \sin(2\pi f_{sc} t + \varphi_{sc}(t)) + \varphi_c(t)) \quad (42)$$

with f_c, f_{sc} being the carrier/subcarrier frequencies, $\varphi_c(t), \varphi_{sc}(t)$ the carrier/subcarrier phase, m_c the

modulation index ($0 < m_c < \pi$), $D(t)$ the information data stream and A the signal amplitude, with $D(t) = \sum_n c_n p(t - nT_s)$, $c_n \in \{+1, -1\}$, T_s symbol period and $p(t)$ the pulse shape. The communication channel is modeled as an AWGN channel in the presence of Doppler and phase noise. The received signal is then given by:

$$r_k = x_k e^{j(2\pi(F_s k T_k + \frac{1}{2} F_r (k T_k)^2) + \phi_{noise})} + n_k, \quad (43)$$

where x_k is the received digital baseband signal and T_k the sample period. The Doppler shift and Doppler rate are denoted by F_s and F_r , respectively. The phase noise ϕ_{noise} is introduced at the simulation by applying a mask similar to the one defined in [76], and AWGN is added according to

$$n_k \sim \text{CN}(0, N_0).$$

To illustrate the potential application of KFs to this case study, the challenging carrier tracking scenario is evaluated by means of Monte Carlo simulations implementing the telecommand link specified in Table I. Figure 8(a) depicts the carrier phase steady state Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for both 2nd and 3rd order PLLs compared to a standard Adaptive KF-based tracking loop. The reference lock refers to the $\sigma = 30^\circ$ loss-of-lock rule-of-thumb [3]. The performance obtained with both PLLs is similar when considering the same loop bandwidth, and slightly worse with the 2nd PLL with a higher bandwidth, as typically considered in the carrier acquisition stage. The performance gain obtained with the AKF is clear from the results, where for this specific case study the performance improvement is higher at lower E_s/N_0 .

Figure 8(b) illustrates the automatic adaptive bandwidth given by the AKF approach versus the constant standard PLL bandwidth (i.e., acquisition mode $Bw = 20$ Hz, tracking mode $Bw = 10$ Hz). When using the latter, the transition between acquisition and tracking modes is performed in an heuristic manner, while the adaptive bandwidth provided by the AKF is based on the optimal filtering solution. Notice that the AKF bandwidth starts at 45 Hz for a fast acquisition and then converges to 7.5 Hz in the steady-state regime.

Although KF approaches can offer advantages over PLL configurations in terms of adaptability it remains for further investigation a more exhaustive analysis on its robustness and complexity requirements for the very low SNR regime.

RF modulation	Remnant carrier, as in (42)
Pulse code modulation	Non-return-to-zero level (NRZ-L)
Carrier frequency	X-band
Subcarrier frequency	$f_{sc} = 16$ kHz
Modulation index	$m_c = 1.2$
Subcarrier waveform	sinusoid
Symbol rate	125 sps
Doppler shift	$F_s = 2$ kHz
Doppler rate	$F_r = 30$ Hz/s

TABLE I

PARAMETERS OF THE DEEP SPACE TELECOMMAND COMMUNICATION LINK USED IN THE SIMULATIONS.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a detailed comparison of PLL and KF-based carrier synchronization techniques, together with some promising advanced architectures, the main goal being to shed some light on the PLL vs KF dilemma and to provide the practitioner with design guidelines. To summarize, below there is a list of the main reasons why KF-based architectures should be preferred in modern receivers operating under non-nominal propagation conditions over PLL legacy schemes:

- Formulated from an optimal filtering approach.

- Inherent adaptive bandwidth architecture.
- Joint carrier phase and frequency optimal estimation.
- Nonlinear implementation operating with the received signal, avoiding possible discriminator disadvantages.
- State-space augmentation to account for prior knowledge on non-nominal propagation conditions.
- Adaptive tracking architectures to cope with challenging time-varying propagation scenarios.
- Easily embedded into a multiple model method.

Even if this paper claims and shows that KF-based architectures are always equivalent or superior in terms of performance with respect to their PLL counterpart, and in general are more flexible and robust, it is worth saying that the latter are still useful in many applications where: non-nominal channel propagation conditions do not apply, the increased computational complexity may not be accepted or the final fine tuning is not possible.

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